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Motor reaction time and accuracy in patients with multiple sclerosis: effects of an active computerized training program

Abstract:

In this study, we aimed to determine the difference of motor reaction time and accuracy between the patients with moderate multiple sclerosis (MS) and healthy subjects and to determine whether a specified cognitive-motor training can improve the speed and accuracy of information processing in patients with MS. A total of 205 patients (30% males) and 276 age-/gender-matched healthy subjects (31% males) were included in the study. Furthermore, using a stratified randomization method, patients with MS were randomly assigned to one of two groups: active information processing training (AIPT) (n = 49) or post-control (n = 55). The AIPT group was asked to complete a computerized visual-manual training program and the post-control group asked to complete the same task without an increase in difficulty. Before and after the intervention phase, the simple, choice, and semantic reaction times and accuracies of all participants were evaluated using the VLS measurement battery. Our results demonstrated that the case and control group were significantly different in terms of the simple, choice, and semantic motor reaction times and accuracies. Compared with the pre-intervention phase, the AIPT and control group's performances in the post-intervention phase were considerably improved in simple, choice, and semantic motor reaction times and choice and semantic motor reaction accuracies. The results also showed that the AIPT group performed significantly better than the post-control group in terms of simple and choice motor reaction times. We showed the positive effects of training on the performance of patients with MS in motor reaction time and accuracy..

Keywords: Motor reaction accuracy; Motor reaction time; Multiple sclerosis; Visual-manual training program.

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